

EXTENT OF PREPAREDNESS OF TOURISM MANAGEMENT STUDENTS FOR INDUSTRY DEMAND

Lengem Mae O. Curativo, Icee May Valerie Sotillo, Jomel M. Garsula,
Tristan Joseph G. Cabano

*Metro Dumaguete College, Dumaguete City
Negros Oriental, 6200, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

Preparedness for industry demands among Tourism Management students is a crucial factor in ensuring success in the professional field. The respondents of this study were fourth-year Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management students from Metro Dumaguete College. This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the students' preparedness for industry demands. Data were collected through a validated researcher-made survey questionnaire administered to 77 selected BS Tourism students. The gathered data were analyzed using the Weighted Mean and Pearson's Rank Correlation Coefficient. The findings revealed that the Tourism Management students demonstrated a very high extent of preparedness in their academic and technical competencies, particularly in hospitality knowledge, practical skills, and communication skills. Similarly, the students exhibited a very high extent of preparedness in their interpersonal and professional competencies, including adaptability and problem-solving, customer service, work ethics and values, cultural awareness and sensitivity, and time management. Furthermore, the results showed a strong and significant relationship between the students' academic and technical competencies and their interpersonal and professional competencies. In general, the study concludes that the students are highly prepared to meet the demands of the tourism industry.

Keywords: *Professional Skills, Interpersonal skills, Industry demand, Academic skills, Technical Skills*

INTRODUCTION

Internships play a vital role in preparing students for industry demands because they enhance the competence and confidence of hotel management students while bridging the gap between academic knowledge and professional practice (Sharma & Sharma, 2025). In the field of hospitality and tourism, students frequently encounter challenges during internships, including communication barriers, workplace adjustment difficulties, lack of confidence, and limited practical exposure, all of which reflect broader global concerns in hospitality education (Vo et al., 2021). In support of this, Saber and Kamaruddin (2025) emphasized through a global bibliometric analysis that training, competencies, and job readiness remain among the most critical themes in hospitality education worldwide.

Students' readiness for employment is greatly influenced by their knowledge, skills, and attitudes, with attitude identified as the most significant factor affecting employability (Alivio et al., 2023). However, many students continue to experience inadequate preparedness in terms of practical competencies, interpersonal communication, adaptability, and professional behavior before entering internship programs and the tourism industry. Employers have consistently emphasized the importance of practical skills, problem-solving abilities, customer service excellence, emotional intelligence, technological literacy, and cultural awareness as essential competencies for employability (Baluyut, 2025). The absence of these competencies may result in poor workplace performance, difficulty adapting to professional environments, low self-confidence, and limited employment opportunities after graduation. Furthermore, although most Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management (BSTM) graduates from Mindoro State University Bongabong Campus obtain jobs related to their field, some still pursue careers outside traditional tourism pathways, suggesting possible gaps in career readiness and professional preparation (Magboo-Campo, 2025).

The study conducted by Sharma (2025) primarily focused on determining how the number and quality of internship experiences influence the self-perceived competence of Hotel Management students in Uttarakhand's five-star hotel industry. In contrast, the present study focused on students' preparedness prior to internship deployment. Specifically, it sought to evaluate the extent to which Tourism Management students possessed the necessary knowledge, technical skills, interpersonal abilities, and professional competencies required to meet industry demands.

The lack of adequate preparedness prior to internship deployment and industry exposure poses a significant concern because it may lead to unsatisfactory training performance, diminished self-efficacy in professional settings, and reduced employability upon graduation. This study is expected to contribute significantly to the improvement of curriculum design, internship programs, and student readiness. By identifying gaps in students' knowledge, technical competencies, interpersonal abilities, and professionalism, the findings may help educators align the curriculum with industry standards, develop more comprehensive and effective pre-internship training programs, and strengthen students' readiness for real-world experiences.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the extent of preparedness of Tourism Management students for industry demand. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent do Tourism Management students exhibit academic and technical skills in terms of:
 - 1.1 knowledge of tourism and hospitality concepts;
 - 1.2 practical and technical skills; and
 - 1.3 communication skills?
2. What is the extent of preparedness of Tourism Management students' interpersonal and professional skills in terms of:
 - 2.1 adaptability and problem-solving skills;
 - 2.2 customer service orientation;
 - 2.3 professional work ethics and values;
 - 2.4 cultural awareness and sensitivity; and
 - 2.5 time management and organizational skills?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of academic and technical preparedness of Tourism Management students and their interpersonal and professional preparedness?

METHODOLOGY

Research design. This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the preparedness of Tourism Management students for industry demands. It was conducted among Tourism students at Metro Dumaguete College. Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire administered to the respondents. The questionnaire measured students' preparedness for industry demands in terms of their academic, technical, professional, and interpersonal skills using a Likert scale. The independent variables included academic skills, technical skills, professional skills, and interpersonal skills, while the dependent variable included the students' preparedness for industry demands. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools to determine the levels of preparedness and to identify significant relationships and patterns among the variables.

Research respondents. The respondents of this study were selected from the fourth-year Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management students of Metro Dumaguete College. These students were chosen because they were considered most appropriate for the study, as they were nearing graduation and were expected to possess sufficient exposure to academic training and internship-related experiences relevant to industry demands. A quota sampling technique was employed to ensure fair and non-biased representation of the target population. This sampling method helped ensure that the required number of respondents was adequately distributed and properly represented within the selected group. A total of 77 respondents were identified as the final sample size of the study. These respondents provided the necessary data for assessing the

extent of preparedness of Tourism Management students in terms of their academic, technical, professional, and interpersonal skills in relation to industry demands.

Research environment. This study was conducted at Metro Dumaguete College, a private higher education institution owned by Dr. Delma P. Manila. The college is located along E.J. Blanco Extension Drive, Daro, Dumaguete City. The institution offers the Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management program and is recognized for having one of the highest student populations in tourism among private higher education institutions in Dumaguete City. It provides academic and practical training designed to prepare students for careers in the tourism and hospitality industry, making it an appropriate setting for this study on students' preparedness for industry demands.

Research instrument. This study utilized a validated, researcher-made questionnaire as the primary research instrument for gathering data from Tourism Management students at Metro Dumaguete College. The questionnaire was designed to assess students' preparedness for industry demands in terms of academic skills, technical skills, professional skills, and interpersonal skills.

The instrument consisted of structured items measured using a 5-point Likert scale to determine the respondents' level of agreement with each statement. The questionnaire was subjected to content validation by experts in tourism education, internship coordinators, and the research director to ensure its relevance, clarity, and appropriateness. To establish reliability, a pilot test (dry run) was conducted prior to the actual data gathering. The internal consistency of the instrument was computed using Cronbach's Alpha, a statistical measure that evaluates the degree of interrelatedness among items in a scale. The value of Cronbach's Alpha ranges from 0 to 1, where higher values indicate greater reliability, and a value of 0.70 or higher is generally considered acceptable.

The results of the pilot testing revealed that all variables demonstrated acceptable levels of internal consistency, as indicated by their Cronbach's Alpha coefficients. This confirmed that the instrument was reliable for use in the actual data collection. The detailed Cronbach's Alpha results are presented below:

Indicators	Cronbach Alpha Value
knowledge and hospitality concepts	0.90
practical and technical skills	0.72
communication skills	0.80
adaptability and problem-solving skills	0.83
customer service orientation	0.80
professional work ethics and values	0.90

cultural awareness and sensitivity	0.87
time management and organizational skills	0.90

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Extent of Tourism Management Students Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills in terms of Knowledge of Tourism and Hospitality Concepts

Knowledge of Tourism and Hospitality Concepts	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
<i>I am ready to...</i>			
1. demonstrate my knowledge of fundamental tourism and hospitality concepts.	4.29	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. apply what I have learned in tourism and hospitality to industry practices.	4.36	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. explain important principles, trends, and issues in tourism and hospitality.	4.25	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. integrate my classroom learning into real-world tourism and hospitality situations.	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. connect my understanding of tourism and hospitality concepts with industry standards.	4.32	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.29	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.1 presents the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills in terms of Knowledge of Tourism and Hospitality Concepts with overall wieghted mean of ($\bar{w}_x = 4.29$), categorized as “very high”.

Table 1.2
Extent of Tourism Management Students Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills in terms of Practical and Technical Skills

Practical and Technical Skills	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
<i>I am ready to...</i>			
1. interact with colleagues, clients, and customers.	4.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. handle unexpected situations and provide better solutions.	4.34	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. prioritize every task and manage my time efficiently.	4.44	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. use software applications, such as booking systems or customer relationship management tools.	4.48	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. adjust to new situations, environment and technologies.	4.42	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.44	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.2 shows the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills in terms of Practical and Technical Skills. with composite mean of ($\bar{w}x = 4.44$),categorized as “very high” .

Table 1.3
Extent of Tourism Management Students Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills in terms of Communication Skill

Communication Skills	$\bar{w}x$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
<i>I am ready to...</i>			
1. speak clearly and confidently when interacting with guests and colleagues.	4.45	Strongly Agree	Very High

2. provide accurate and understandable information to guests when responding to their inquiries.	4.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. attentively listen and address guests concerns.	4.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. communicate effectively with people coming from different countries and with different cultural backgrounds.	4.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. face and talk with guests who have complaints calmly and respectfully.	4.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.52	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.3 reveals the perceived extent of effectiveness for the industry demand with the students' communication skills. The composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.52$), categorized as "very high" .

Table 2.2
Extent of Tourism Management Students' Interpersonal and Professional Skills in terms of Customer Service Orientation

Customer Service Orientation	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
<i>I am ready to...</i>			
1. communicate clearly with customers.	4.53	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. listen actively to guest needs.	4.53	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. handle customer concerns with patience.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. pay attention to the needs of guests.	4.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. make guests feel welcome and satisfied.	4.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.56	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.2 illustrates the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of customer service orientation with a composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.56$).

Table 2.3
Extent of Tourism Management Students' Interpersonal and Professional Skills in terms of Professional Work Ethics and Values

Professional Work Ethics and Values	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
<i>I am ready to...</i>			
1. be on time and complete my duties.	4.51	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. follow company rules and instructions.	4.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. respect my co-workers and supervisors.	4.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. take responsibility for my actions at work.	4.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. act with honesty and professionalism in all tasks.	4.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.3 displays the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of professional and work ethics values with the composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$).

Table 2.4
Extent of Tourism Management Students' Interpersonal and Professional Skills in terms of Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity

Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
<i>I am ready to...</i>			
1. adapt my behavior to respect and value the diverse cultural backgrounds.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High

2. respect and value guests and colleagues' culture.	4.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. treat people as individuals while being mindful of cultural norms.	4.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. pay attention without interrupting.	4.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. ask respectful questions when appropriate.	4.64	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.4 exposes the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of cultural awareness and sensitivity with composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.57$), categorized as “very high” .

Table 2.5
Extent of Tourism Management Students' Interpersonal and Professional Skills in terms of Time Management and Organizational Skills

Time Management and Organizational Skills	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
<i>I am ready to...</i>			
1. identify which task needs first attention.	4.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. review what I have accomplished and adjust plans to improve.	4.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. focus on important and urgent task.	4.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. handle diverse tasks with accuracy and present high-quality work.	4.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. finish the task efficiently and on time.	4.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.56	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Extent of Effectiveness
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.5 presents the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of Time Management and Organizational Skills with the composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.56$),categorized as “very high”.

Table 3
Significant Relationship between the Extent of Academic and Technical Preparedness of Tourism Management Students and their Interpersonal and Professional Preparedness

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Knowledge of Tourism and Hospitality Concepts				
Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills	0.450	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Customer Service Orientation	0.263	0.021	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Professional Work Ethics and Values	0.313	0.006	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity	0.327	0.004	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Time Management and Organizational Skills	0.416	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Practical and Technical Skills				
Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills	0.490	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Customer Service Orientation	0.266	0.020	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Professional Work Ethics and Values	0.331	0.003	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity	0.323	0.004	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Time Management and Organizational Skills	0.361	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Communication Skills				
Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills	0.491	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Customer Service Orientation	0.444	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Professional Work Ethics and Values	0.345	0.002	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity	0.576	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Time Management and Organizational Skills	0.479	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Table 3 shows data in assessing the significant relationships between the extent of academic and technical preparedness of Tourism Management students and their interpersonal and professional preparedness. Using Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient, it is evident that all p-values are less than the level of significance (0.05). This exposes the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that significant relationships exist between students’ academic and technical preparedness and their interpersonal and professional preparedness.

DISCUSSION

Extent of Tourism Management Students Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills

1.1 Knowledge of Tourism and Hospitality Concepts

Table 1.1 presents the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills in terms of Knowledge of Tourism and Hospitality Concepts with overall wieghted mean of ($w\bar{x}=4.29$), categorized as “very high”. Specifically, students perceived extent of preparedness in applying what have learned in tourism and hospitality to industry practices with the highest weighted mean of 4.36, followed by connecting understanding of tourism and hospitality concepts with industry standards ($w\bar{x}=4.32$), demonstrating knowledge of fundamental tourism and hospitality concepts ($w\bar{x}=4.29$), explaining relevant principles, trends, and issues in tourism and hospitality ($w\bar{x}=4.25$) and integrating classroom learning into real-world tourism and hospitality situations with the lowest mean of 4.23. This suggest that students feel positively about the extent preparedness for industry demand in exhibiting academic and technical skills in terms of knowledge of tourism and hospitality concepts. Tourism students need a balanced mix of knowledge, skills, and attitude to meet industry demands. Attitude is key, but all three areas must be refreshed through a program with local and international exposure (Mira et al.,2023). In this case, higher education institutions play an important role in developing students' knowledge and skills based on industry needs. Strong academic foundations are essential for preparing capable tourism professionals (Roma, 2021). Besides, students are prepared for industry demands through a curriculum balancing knowledge (hospitality concepts) and skills, aligning with industry standards and dynamic needs, ensuring they're job-ready upon graduation (Putra et al., 2022).

1.2 Practical and Technical Skills

Table 1.2 shows the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on Exhibiting Academic and Technical Skills in terms of Practical and Technical Skills. with composite mean of ($w\bar{x} = 4.44$),categorized as “very high” . Specifically students perceived extent of preparedness in interact with colleagues-clients, and customers with a highest weighted mean of 4.52 , followed by using software applications,($w\bar{x} = 4.42$), prioritize every task and manage my time efficiently($w\bar{x} = 4.48$), adjust to new situations, environment and technologies($w\bar{x} = 4.32$) , and handle unexpected situations and provide better solution with the lowest weighted mean 4.34. This states that the students' preparedness for Industry demand are positive with their practical and technical skills. To meet future workforce needs, it is essential for academic institutions in tourism and hospitality to stay informed about the skills and education required for their employees. Traditional internship evaluations in vocational colleges often suffer from limited data, vague criteria, and delayed

feedback (Liu, 2025). Hudson (2025) states that improved student and school outcomes depend on high-quality leadership preparation programs, with principal internships playing a critical role in providing hands-on experiences that develop effective future school leaders. Thus, the organization of practical training for students is associated with several significant social outcomes. These include improving the employability and competitiveness of graduates in the labor market, enhancing the overall quality of services in the tourism and hospitality sector, promoting the adoption of innovative practices within the industry, and supporting the establishment of entrepreneurial ventures (Radygina, 2023).

1.3 Communication Skills

Table 1.3 reveals the perceived extent of effectiveness for the industry demand with the students' communication skills. The composite mean of ($wx = 4.52$), categorized as "very high". The results shows that students are very attentive in listening and addressing guest concerns, which got the highest mean ($wx = 4.58$), followed by facing and talking with guests who have complaints calmly and respectfully ($wx = 4.55$), providing accurate and understandable information to guests when responding to their inquiries ($wx = 4.52$), communicate effectively with people coming from different countries and with different cultural backgrounds ($wx = 4.49$), and speaking clearly and confidently when interacting with guests and colleagues ($wx = 4.45$). This suggest that students are prepared for the industry demand with their communication skills. The results show that communication skills are essential for Tourism Management students because these skills enable them to interact effectively with people from diverse cultural backgrounds (Rachim & Salam, 2025). In the tourism and hospitality industry, employees should be carefully selected and continuously trained, as their communication skills play a vital role in fostering positive customer interactions (Tankovic et al., 2022). Furthermore, tourism service providers must demonstrate strong communication skills to effectively deliver quality services and ensure satisfying and enjoyable experiences for tourists (Tankovic et al., 2021).

Extent of Tourism Management Students' Interpersonal and Professional Skills

2.1 Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills

Table 2.1 indicates the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills with the composite mean of ($wx = 4.51$), categorized as "very high". Specifically, students' preparedness shows a "very high extent" in responding calmly to guests' concerns and ensure guests' satisfactions with the highest weighted mean of 4.65, followed by apply what have learned in the classroom to real settings with weighted mean of 4.60. The effective collaboration with fellow interns

with weighted mean of 4.49. Working with people with diverse personalities ($wx = 4.45$) and adjust quickly from one task to another with the lowest weighted mean of 4.34. This indicate that students are prepared and positively confident for the industry demand with their Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills. The holistic development of students plays a vital role in education, influencing both their health and overall quality of life, physical education serves as a key element in fostering motor skills such as agility, endurance, and coordination, while also promoting an appreciation for physical activity as a foundation for a healthy lifestyle (Nicolaiuc, 2025). Cultural tourism preserves traditions and promotes global understanding, but engaging younger generations requires interactive digital experiences due to shifting preferences shaped by social media and digital entertainment (Liamruk et al., 2025). Problem-solving and adaptability are considered essential competencies that education should develop among learners, as these skills enable them to address challenges and adjust to changing environments effectively (Liwanag & Lunar, 2023).

2.2 Customer Service Orientation

Table 2.2 illustrates the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of customer service orientation with a composite mean of ($wx = 4.56$). Specifically, students preparedness shows a “very high” in making guests feel welcome and satisfied as the highest weighted mean ($wx = 4.60$), pay attention to the needs of guests ($wx = 4.58$), handle customer concerns with patience ($wx = 4.57$) and communicate clearly with customers as the lowest weight mean ($wx = 4.53$). This suggest that students feel positively about the extent preparedness for industry demand in interpersonal and professional skills in terms of customer service orientation. However, the lack of qualified personnel in the tourism sector continues to negatively affect service quality, a situation further aggravated by the limited number of tourism-trained staff and the tendency of graduates to leave the industry. Consequently, studies have explored the relationship between employees’ customer service orientation and their intention to pursue careers in tourism (Güven et al., 2025).

2.3 Professional Work Ethics and Values

Table 2.3 displays the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of professional and work ethics values with the composite mean of ($wx = 4.57$). Specifically, students preparedness show a “ver high ” extent in being honest and professional with the highest weighted mean ($wx = 4.65$), respecting colleagues ($wx = 4.58$), take responsibility and follow company rules with both weighted mean of 4.55 , and being on time and complete duties with the lowest weighted mean 4.51. Human values help Tourism Management students develop ethical behavior, guide appropriate

interactions with guests and colleagues, foster respect for individuals from diverse backgrounds, and encourage the delivery of assistance and quality service to others (Kumar & Bhinder, 2026). Furthermore, quality of work life positively impacts hotel employees' performance, motivation, satisfaction, self-efficacy, and work ethics, with these factors significantly enhancing overall job performance (Putra et al., 2021). In addition, ethics remain a significant concern for both individuals and organizations because they help establish trust and professionalism. Consequently, students should receive proper training to ensure the consistent application of ethical practices when interacting with guests (Aslam et al., 2025).

2.4 Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity

Table 2.4 exposes the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of cultural awareness and sensitivity with composite mean of ($wx = 4.57$), categorized as "very high". Specifically students perceived a very extent of preparedness in asking respectful questions when appropriate ($wx = 4.64$), respect and value guests and colleagues' culture ($wx = 4.58$), adapt behavior to respect and value the diverse cultural backgrounds ($wx = 4.57$), treat people as individuals while being mindful of cultural norms ($wx = 4.55$), and pay attention without interrupting ($wx = 4.52$). This suggest that students feel positively about the extent preparedness for industry demand in interpersonal and professional skills in terms of cultural awareness and sensitivity. Tourism education helps students develop cultural and social awareness, enabling them to interact effectively with individuals from diverse backgrounds. Furthermore, cultural awareness involves recognizing and valuing cultural differences while possessing the appropriate knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to address cultural gaps (Trang & Phuong, 2023). Sustainable tourism and cultural events raise heritage awareness, attract visitors, boost the economy, strengthen social bonds, preserve cultural identity, and promote environmental consciousness (Nguyen 2025).

2.5 Time Management and Organizational Skills

Table 2.5 presents the extent to which students perceived effectiveness for industry demand. The result indicate that tourism management students perceived extent preparedness for industry demand on their interpersonal and professional skills in terms of Time Management and Organizational Skills with the composite mean of ($wx = 4.56$), categorized as "very high". Specifically students perceived a very high extent of preparedness in finishing the task efficiently and on time ($wx = 4.60$), handle tasks with accuracy and present high-quality work ($wx = 4.57$), focus on important task ($wx = 4.56$), reviewing accomplishments and plans for improvement ($wx = 4.55$), and identify which task needs first attention ($wx = 4.52$). This suggest that students feel positively about the extent preparedness for industry demand in interpersonal and professional

skills in terms of Time Management and Organizational Skills. Effective time management is an important factor in the academic success and overall well-being of Tourism Management students. According to Ghafar (2024), effective time management is essential because human energy and physical strength diminish over time, making it important to accomplish tasks within a specific period and emphasizing the need to live and act in the present moment to maintain effectiveness. The use of technology helps create a more engaging and relevant learning environment, providing teachers with greater opportunities to diversify their teaching methods and enhance student learning outcomes (Bagon et al., 2023).

Relationship between the extent of academic and technical preparedness of Tourism Management students and their interpersonal and professional preparedness

Table 3 shows data in assessing the significant relationships between the extent of academic and technical preparedness of Tourism Management students and their interpersonal and professional preparedness. Using Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, it is evident that all p-values are less than the level of significance (0.05). This exposes the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that significant relationships exist between students' academic and technical preparedness and their interpersonal and professional preparedness. In terms of knowledge of tourism and hospitality concepts, students' adaptability and problem-solving skills ($r = 0.450$, $p = 0.001$), customer service orientation ($r = 0.263$, $p = 0.021$), professional work ethics and values ($r = 0.313$, $p = 0.006$), cultural awareness and sensitivity ($r = 0.327$, $p = 0.004$), and time management and organizational skills ($r = 0.416$, $p = 0.001$) all demonstrate significant positive relationships. This suggests that a stronger understanding of tourism and hospitality concepts is associated with higher interpersonal and professional competence among students. Regarding practical and technical skills, positive correlations were observed with adaptability and problem-solving skills ($r = 0.490$, $p = 0.001$), customer service orientation ($r = 0.266$, $p = 0.020$), professional work ethics and values ($r = 0.331$, $p = 0.003$), cultural awareness and sensitivity ($r = 0.323$, $p = 0.004$), and time management and organizational skills ($r = 0.361$, $p = 0.001$). This indicates that hands-on technical proficiency in tourism and hospitality tasks contributes significantly to students' interpersonal and professional effectiveness. For communication skills, the data shows significant relationships across all measured interpersonal and professional skills, including adaptability and problem-solving skills ($r = 0.491$, $p = 0.001$), customer service orientation ($r = 0.444$, $p = 0.001$), professional work ethics and values ($r = 0.345$, $p = 0.002$), cultural awareness and sensitivity ($r = 0.576$, $p = 0.001$), and time management and organizational skills ($r = 0.479$, $p = 0.001$). This underscores the critical role of communication skills in enhancing both professional behavior and interpersonal effectiveness in tourism management contexts. Tourism Management students must be adequately prepared to meet industry demands, contribute to economic growth, and deliver exceptional guest experiences. To succeed in the dynamic tourism and hospitality sector, students need a comprehensive understanding of hospitality services, including accommodation operations and food and beverage management (Sampaio et al., 2024).

Furthermore, tailored programs such as internships and mentorship opportunities help students recognize their skills and competencies while bridging the gap between academic learning and industry expectations (Martini et al., 2026). Pantaruk et al., (2025), states that foundational competencies such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving are critical for enhancing students' readiness to meet the dynamic demands of the hospitality industry. In addition, understanding students' motivations may help institutions provide better support systems that enhance employability and strengthen Work-Integrated Learning (WIL) preparation for industry demands (Jackson, 2024). The findings highlight that academic knowledge, practical skills, and communication competencies play a vital role in the holistic professional development of Tourism Management students. Moreover, these competencies contribute significantly to students' preparedness for the tourism and hospitality industry. Therefore, educational institutions should continue integrating technical training with opportunities that strengthen interpersonal and professional skills to ensure that graduates are well-equipped to meet evolving industry demands.

Conclusions

The findings revealed that the students demonstrated a very high level of preparedness in both academic and technical skills, as well as in interpersonal and professional skills. Specifically, the students showed strong knowledge of tourism and hospitality concepts, practical and technical abilities, and communication skills, indicating their readiness to perform industry-related tasks. Likewise, they exhibited very high levels of adaptability, problem-solving skills, customer service orientation, professional and work ethics, cultural awareness and sensitivity, and time management and organizational skills. However, based on the indicators with relatively lower mean scores, areas such as consistent application of advanced problem-solving strategies, higher-level adaptability in complex and unfamiliar situations, and more refined time management and organizational efficiency still require further enhancement. These suggest that while students are generally well-prepared, there remain specific competencies that need continuous development to fully meet industry expectations. Furthermore, the results revealed a significant relationship between academic and technical preparedness and interpersonal and professional preparedness, indicating that the development of one area supports and strengthens the other. This underscores the importance of a balanced and holistic approach to student development. In general, the findings indicate that Tourism Management students possess strong and relevant competencies aligned with industry demands, while also highlighting specific areas that require continued improvement to further enhance their overall preparedness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study on the extent of preparedness of Tourism Management students for industry demand, the researchers recommend the following to the students, schools administrators and Deans, and future researchers:

Students. May further strengthen their problem-solving skills, adaptability in complex situations, and time management efficiency by actively engaging in experiential learning activities such as simulations, internships, and real-life tourism and hospitality scenarios. These experiences may help them enhance decision-making, flexibility, and productivity in professional settings.

School Administrators/Deans. May enhance curriculum delivery by implementing targeted interventions such as workshops, simulation-based training, and industry immersion activities that focus on developing students' critical thinking, adaptability, and organizational skills. Strengthening these areas may better prepare graduates for the demands of the tourism industry.

Future Researchers. May explore the factors influencing students' problem-solving, adaptability, and time management competencies and conduct intervention-based or comparative studies across institutions.

Compliance with ethical standards

The study entitled "Extent of Preparedness of Tourism Management Students' for Industry Demand" strictly adhered to ethical principles and guidelines for research involving human participants.

All participants were provided with comprehensive and transparent information regarding the study's objectives, methodologies, and their rights to participate voluntarily. Before administering the questionnaire, we ensured that written informed consent was obtained from each respondent, as clearly outlined in the introductory section of the instrument.

The researchers treated all collected responses with the highest level of confidentiality. No personally identifiable information was disclosed or included in the presentation of the findings. Research data were securely stored and accessible only to the research team. Following the completion of the study's presentation and defense, all survey materials were permanently disposed of through shredding, ensuring the utmost data privacy and integrity.

Moreover, the institution acknowledged the responsible deployment of artificial intelligence technologies to foster academic innovation, enhance research processes, and streamline administrative functions. AI tools were exclusively utilized for language editing and document formatting purposes. The authors retained full ownership of all intellectual contributions and scholarly input.

Acknowledgements

The researchers would like to extend their deepest and sincerest gratitude to the following people who in one way or another have shared their time and effort for the success of this study:

First and foremost, the researchers extend their heartfelt appreciation to their research advisers Ms. Abigail V. Santisteban and Mr. Jackson Repollo, and research instructor Mr. Renze O. Lagrada for the invaluable guidance, patience and for constant support throughout the entire research process.

Sincere appreciation to the President of Metro Dumaguete College Dr. Delma P. Manila CESO V and the College of Tourism Management Dean Ms. Maricar D. Morqueda, MBA for allowing the researchers and supporting them in conducting their study.

To the panelist Dr. Eva C. Melon, Dr. Cristina P. Calisang, and Ms. Maricar D. Morqueda, for providing critical insights and valuable comments that helped and enriched this research effectively.

Special acknowledgement is given to the respondents for their honesty in sharing their thoughts during the survey.

The researchers thank their families and friends for unwavering support and understanding throughout the research process.

Lastly, the ALMIGHTY FATHER for the wisdom and for His undeniable presence that never left the researchers throughout their academic journey.

REFERENCES

- Alivio, M., Parra, J. K., & Esplanada, D. E. (2023). Student readiness to enter tourism and hospitality industry. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8037547>
- Amanda Rizka Rachim & Dicky Arsyul Salam. (2025) Building Better Communication in Tourism: How Cultural Competence and Language Skills Shape Service Performance <https://doi.org/10.35313/jtospolban.v5i1.153>
- Aslam, Masood & Kumar, Nirbhay & Singh, Jitendra & Priya, Nishi. (2025). professional ethics in hospitality industry. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393842490_professional_ethics_in_hospitality_industry
- Bagon, M., Samillano, J., & Tinapay, A. (2023). Assessing the competence and skills of hospitality and tourism management students https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368476813_assessing_the_competence_and_skills_of_hospitality_and_tourism_management_students
- Baluyut, P. (2025). Bridging the Gap: Preparing Students for the Real World of Tourism and Hospitality Management at State Universities. *International Journal on Culture, History, and Religion*, 7(SI3), 225–238. <https://doi.org/10.63931/ijchr.v7iSI3.322>
- Cuic Tankovic, A., Kapeš, J., & Benazić, D. (2022). Measuring the importance of communication skills in tourism economic research <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677x.2022.2077790>
- Čuić Tanković, Ana & Kapeš, Jelena & Kraljić, Valentina. (2021). Importance of soft skills and communication skills in tourism: viewpoint from tourists and future tourism employees. <https://doi.org/10.20867/tosee.06.12>
- Ghafar, Z. (2024). The relevance of time management in academic achievement: a critical review of the literature. <https://doi.org/10.59890/ijasr.v1i4.1008>
- Güven, Selda & Mazlum, Berna & Cesur, Esra & Aycan, Merv & Şahin, Seda. (2025). The role of service orientation in shaping tourism students' willingness to work within the sector. <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18106632>

- Hudson, M. A. (2025). Examining perceptions of educational leadership skills in principal internship experiences. *international journal of educational leadership preparation* <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=importance+of+practical+skills+for+internship&ft=on&id=EJ1476605>
- Jackson, D. (2024). The relationship between student employment, employability-building activities and graduate outcomes. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2023.2253426>
- Joesri Mohamad Saber, Kardina Kamaruddin (2025). A Bibliometric Analysis of Training, Competencies, and Job Readiness in the Hotel and Tourism Industry: Trends and Future Directions. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 9(14), 282-297. <https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2025.914MG0023>
- Kumar, V., & Bhinder, H. S. (2026). Examine the impact of curriculum components on students' employability potential: A study on undergraduate tourism students. *Atna Journal of Tourism Studies*, 35(3), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.12727/ajts.35.3>
- Liamruk, P., Onwong, N., Amornrat, K., Arayapipatkul, A., & Sipiyanuk, K. (2025). Development and evaluation of an augmented reality serious game to enhance 21st century skills in cultural tourism. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-95615-5>
- Liu, Y. (2025). Research on intelligent evaluation system for internship quality in higher vocational colleges based on multi-source data fusion. *international journal of emerging technologies and advanced applications*. <https://doi.org/10.62677/IJETAA.2509139>
- Liwanag, M. J., & Lunar, B. (2023). College of arts and sciences students' levels of problem solving, collaboration and adaptability skills: basis for curriculum enhancement. *education, sustainability & society*. <https://doi.org/10.26480/ess.02.2023.82.86>
- Magboo-Campo, C. (2025). Employability pathways among tourism management graduates: a tracer study. Mindoro State University–Bongabong campus. <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2025.907000280>
- Margie Roma. (2021). Redefining assessment in tourism and hospitality education. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 10(4), 113–121. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v10n4p113>
- Martini M, Tomasuolo M, Marafioti E (2026;), "Enhancing students' perceived employability through employer engagement events in higher education: evidence from a quasi-experimental study". <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-02-2025-0113>
- Mira A. Alivio, Jade Kathleen P. Parra, & Deogracias E. Esplanada. (2023). Student Readiness to Enter Tourism and Hospitality Industry. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8037547>
- Näppä, A., Styvén, M. E., & Robertson, J. (2025). Employment in the tourism and hospitality industry: Toward a unified value proposition. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 24(1), 26–56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332845.2024.2405804>
- Nguyen, T. P. (2025). The impact of sustainable tourism on local community cultural heritage conservation awareness in Hanoi. *heritage and sustainable development* <https://doi.org/10.37868/hsd.v7i2.1233>
- Nicolaiciuc, N. (2025). The development of students' motor skills in the discipline of hiking tourism, in the context of the implementation of the new physical education curriculum in the republic of Moldova <https://doi.org/10.52449/soh23.41>
- Putra, Fajar & Saepudin, Pudir & Utami, Ni. (2022). Preferred Competencies for Tourism and Hospitality Graduates: Evidence from Longitudinal Tracer Studies. <https://doi.org/10.30880/jtet.2022.14.03.009>
- Putra, I. N. T. D., Ardika, I. W., Antara, M., Idrus, S., & Hulfa, I. (2021). The effects of quality of work life on job performance, work motivation, work ethics, job satisfaction, and self-

- efficacy of hotel employees in lombok. *asia-pacific journal of innovation in hospitality and tourism* <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2021.6.5.1034>
- Radygina, E. G. (2023). Practical training model for students in tourism and hospitality: Description of the elements of the practical training system at the university. <https://jhrms.com/index.php/HRMS/article/view/3372>
- Sampaio, C., Sebastião, J. R., & Farinha, L. (2024). Hospitality and Tourism Demand: Exploring Industry Shifts, Themes, and Trends. *Societies*, 14(10), 207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc14100207>
- Sharma, P., & Sharma, M. (2025). Enhancing competence through internships: a study on the correlation between internship experience and competence perceptions among hotel management students. <https://doi.org/10.63931/ijchr.v7iSI3.322>
- Sirinan Pantaruk, Bussalin Khuadthong, Narinthon Imjai, Somnuk Aujirapongpan (2025) Fostering future-ready professionals: The impact of soft skills and internships on hospitality employability in Thailand, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101371>
- Trang, T. T. T., & Phuong, V. T. (2023). Needs analysis about intercultural communicative competence among undergraduate tourism students. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 52,2599–2620. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-023-10012-1>
- Vo, N., Le, L., & Lam, V. (2021). Challenges for student satisfaction of internship program in hospitality and tourism industry in vietnam. *Journal of quality assurance in hospitality&tourism*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1528008X.2021.1964414>